

A federated FAIR platform enabling large-scale analysis of high-value cohort data connecting Europe and Canada in personalized health

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Assessing the current situation based on qualitative research (interviews and observations) with project partners and (external) stakeholders including challenges and opportunities. Proposing concrete recommendations such as creating new roles (eg. data governance manager).

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Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium, **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

- *Document Abbreviations*

AM	Assembly of Members
BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
DoA	Description of Action
CA	Consortium Agreement
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
ECOUTER	Employing Conceptual schema for policy and translation engagement in research
ENSURE	EUCAN-Connect Sustainability Ethnography
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GAG	Governance Advisory Group
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ITN	Innovative Training Network
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PAB	Project Advisory Board
PB	Project Board
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI	Research Infrastructure
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
QRM	Quality and Risk Management
TL	Task Leader
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
USA	United States of America
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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1. Executive summary

This document outlines recommendations on sustainability relevant for EUCAN-Connect (sustainability plan). It presents the current situation based on qualitative research (ECOUTER, interviews and observations) with project partners as well as internal and external stakeholders. It assesses challenges and opportunities and proposes sustainability recommendations during and after the project in ways that can help to sustain achievements of this project in the mid to long term (e.g., what to consider in next projects, how to reach sustainability of tools and expertise). Understanding sustainability not as a one time achievable goal but a moving target, this report proposes specific actions such as training and role descriptions and general recommendations. The analysis focuses on the current landscape, potential users with the future organisation in horizon, even if funding remains based on projects. In this regard, the report has been structured in three pillars: community, financial and organisational sustainability. The findings on opportunities and challenges will be complemented by an upcoming paper that discusses sustainability and value making. The results of this work will inform D6.9 and MS22 which focus on concrete sustainability actions and governance assessment.

2. Introduction

Open science is a policy priority for the European Commission and similar focus on open science is also observed in Canada (see for a review: Austin, 2020), the USA (e.g., National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine, 2018), and globally via international organisations (e.g., UNESCO, 2021). In Europe, it is understood as the standard method of working under the EU's research and innovation funding programmes and is expected to improve the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of research; for instance, as one of the 8 ambitions of the EU's open science policy, open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data) data should become the default for the results of EU-funded scientific research.¹ However, scholars have raised concerns that FAIR should not only be fair, but FAIRER with the addition of *ethical and reproducible* or *equitable and responsible* as further characterising elements of this mode of research (Austin, 2020; Murtagh et al., 2021) while acknowledging the biological materials and data as unified resource for health, transforming FAIR to FAIR-Health (Holub et al., 2018).

While open science, data, software and tools among others are being promoted for a variety of reasons by various actors globally, the recent COVID-19 pandemic has proven an important case of necessity for urgent collaboration and rapid deployment of data sharing infrastructures, reaffirming the previous international recommendations on health data governance (OECD, 2022) and leading scholars across domains to intensify their efforts. One example is that of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) where scholars not only note specific circumstances that different disciplines (i.e. clinical, omics, epidemiology, social sciences) may require during data sharing but also observe cross-cutting issues (i.e. community participation, indigenous data, research software, legal and ethical considerations) that are relevant for all (Austin et al., 2020; RDA COVID-19 Working Group, 2020).

Considering the above, entire networks, from sharing infrastructure to data itself and taking into account diverse arrays of issues are necessary for the implementation, functioning and continued success of fairer sharing for health. While such networks necessitate funding and human resources, along with data and technical infrastructures, their setup should be accompanied with a sustainability perspective (see for instance the recommendations of European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures Long-Term Sustainability Working Group, 2017) that foresees both needs of the future as well as developing resilience within a changing environment and against a diverse array of risks (see for instance a typology of risks in biobanking infrastructures: Akyüz et al., 2021). In this regard, following the responsible research and innovation (RRI) approach, assessment and anticipation of implications and expectations is vital as well as the acceptance by and support of both scientific community and societal actors as key stakeholders.

¹ See (17.10.2022):

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

2.1. Purpose

The major objectives of this report are as follows:

- To report on the findings of stakeholder engagement, qualitative interviews and observations from a sustainability perspective;
- To outline a set of sustainability recommendations within and beyond the project's lifespan.

2.2. Intended Audience

This document is to be used as a reference for:

- all consortium partners of EUCAN-Connect;
- maintainers of participating catalogues;
- current and future consortia embarking on transnational federated data sharing;
- multi-centre cohort studies;
- hosting institutions² and funding agencies³.

3. Methods

The report is mainly based on the qualitative research conducted in WP7. The empirical data collected and analysed include:

- Interviews, in particular micro-interviews conducted during the EUCAN-Connect project kick-off meeting (March 2019) (n=24), and semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders from the EUCAN-Connect consortium, representatives from cohorts, DataSHIELD experts on data access and harmonisation (n= 16, RP2). Interviews were transcribed and analysed. Interview excerpts are coded (e.g., P018) and selected in a manner in order not to disclose the identity of the interview partner.
- ECOUSER stakeholder engagement exercises (Murtagh et al. 2017) and workshops with EUCAN-Connect consortium members at meetings in 2019, 2020, and 2021, as well as with BBMRI Stakeholder Forum Patient Pillar members (Antwerp, Belgium) and African stakeholders in 2019 (Abuja, Nigeria).
- The methodology combines studying ethical, legal, and social questions as well as engaging various stakeholders before the translation of research into practice, with the aim to develop an appropriate governance framework as a co-production. The

² Hosting institution can be an institution which is the legal entity of where the cohort is maintained (e.g., research hospital) or a network of cohorts (e.g., research infrastructure under the ERIC legal framework).

³ A funding agency can be at the regional, national or European level or private, e.g., a patient-run entity.

method uses interactive mind-mapping in a group setting, and was realised face-to-face and online.

- Interviews and ECOUTER sessions were recorded and analysed by WP7 researchers in group settings to identify emerging themes. All data were collected based on the informed consent of participants. The empirical study in WP7 (EUCAN-Connect Sustainability Ethnography (ENSURE)) was approved by the Newcastle University Ethics Committee [Ref: 11381/2018].

This work will be complemented with an upcoming paper that will discuss sustainability and value making.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. From qualitative work to suggestions for sustainability

Following the definition of DataSHIELD on its website as “a novel technological solution that can address some of the most basic challenges in facilitating the access of researchers and other health care professionals to individual level data” and its versatility to be used across domains, “where microdata (data on individual subjects) must be analysed but cannot physically be shared with the research users”, it is positioned ideally within the necessities and opportunities of an openness approach, as “a flexible, modular, free, open-source solution.”⁴ It should also be noted that DataSHIELD is neither a solely technical solution in isolation since it relies on a strong governance process, and health-related data is only one example of many kinds of sensitive data; therefore, the hope is for it to gain wider applicability and use. However, the necessity for constant research funding and stakeholder support, training and continued maintenance of human resources show that sustainability is a multifaceted and complex phenomenon, the discussion of which cannot be limited to financial aspects. Based on the qualitative analysis conducted, which will be discussed in detail in an upcoming manuscript, we have identified the following themes (Figure 1).

While the qualitative research part will be discussed further elsewhere, we would like to briefly contextualise a few examples from this. *Temporality* was one of the key concepts that emerged as central to the discussions with the participants. On the one hand, it relates to the critique of the proceduralisation and bureaucratisation that are part and parcel of research practice as well as the time it takes to accomplish often seemingly simple tasks. On the other hand it highlights the different temporal frames that individuals across institutions and institutions themselves have as one participant puts it:

“Because that access committee will say ‘oh, the users are always sending partial information and we cannot provide them access because it takes so much time for them to answer [...] our question’. And the users will say ‘yeah it takes so long, it

⁴ See (17.10.2022): <https://www.datashield.org/about/about-datashield-collated>

takes one year to have an answer if we can have access or not to the study so I lost my grant because I waited too long’.” – P005

Figure 1. Key themes identified from the preliminary analysis of the qualitative research conducted.

In this regard, while technical solutions can be well designed, the human-to-human exchange is a fundamental component that has to be taken into account in practice. In other words, while cohorts are seen as ‘objects’, actors or entities that can be signified with the term ‘the cohort’, there is more to what meets the eye as the process of sharing often necessitates numerous tasks, decisions and varying responsibilities at the cohort-level as well as other levels. One participant sees a necessity in translating the functioning practices for a post-consortium agreement temporal frame, making the processes and networks durable:

“So how you work together with each other, with each other’s data but at the end we want to get rid of the consortium agreement because it’s only valid during the consortium and not after that. And just make some open agreement between cohorts, a one pager, based on the experiences from the consortium agreements.” – P003

This does not mean, however, that the practices are always optimal within the project-phase despite the gained experience from the previous ones. In many cases, the need to tackle issues earlier on within the project allows identifying some of the key actions that are central for sustainability:

“Because before arriving to DataSHIELD and the analysis it can take up to several years to () the problem with the harmonisation is that the time required to access DataSHIELD or not, set up the infrastructure, (are they OK) on the ethical side, DataSHIELD or not, and organise all that, people always think it will take two months but it takes two years. So what happened in [project X], what happened in [project Y...] is that we finished the harmonisation six months before the end of the project because everybody was late back at the beginning because they were not defining their research questions so to be able to identify which variable we need and ask for access to the data we need the research question. And they all say ‘yeah, yeah, we want to study stress’ OK, stress, stress is what? Stress and what? What are the variables around? So that can take two months to define but the investigator do not take enough time to think about it the first year. And if they don't and they define what they want in the third year - you know! The work can (work in just) the third year, and that's often a problem.” – P005

As the above quote suggests, the work that the process entails may be underestimated or does not match the timing of the planned course of action, especially considering the need for harmonisation, as one of the fundamental issues.

Along with and in addition to the analysis of the qualitative material, for long-term sustainability, we have at least noted that there is a need for new roles and personnel as the lack of resources and expertise came up as an important issue that needed to be tackled. The role descriptions (key responsibilities and accountabilities of the role and requirements) for data managers and ethics managers for supporting users are provided in the Annex 1 and Annex 2, respectively. While these have been discussed within the consortium through ECOUSER engagement exercises and mind mapping exercises, we have noted the need for training for researchers in these issues, i.e. data management and ethics management.

Below sections address sustainability from the viewpoint of the community as well as the financial and the organisational aspects, especially supporting previous qualitative work with a MURAL discussion exercise on 13.10.2022 (see Annex 3).

4.2. Community sustainability

In science, communities are sometimes understood as people producing together or individuals comprising a community of practice (Gläser 2001; Wenger 2010). One participant observes the following: “So that's sort of the dream and the dream was to basically can we not create a community of people with the same problem as we have - or maybe as I have - and try to work together” (P030). In this sense, what brings people together within the

project is partially their sharing of a common problem and possibly their agreement for a common solution or sets of solutions.

Already for many decades, science is more and more understood to be one that is or that strives for being interdisciplinary, application/problem-oriented, socially-robust, and certainly not restricted to an elite group of scientists but includes directly engaging with societal stakeholders (see e.g. the discussions of Mode 1 vs. Mode 2: Gibbons et al., 1994; Nowotny et al., 2001). In this regard, sustainability in science is also tied to sustainability of the community, broadly speaking and includes at least the following as noted in the Grant Agreement: “1) the public (especially patients, biobanks and cohort research participants, patient and disease-focused interest groups); 2) healthcare practitioners and providers (clinicians, public health workers and managers); 3) policy and implementation practitioners (local and national health policymakers); and 4) the research and translation community (researchers, funders, local research translation groups)” (EUCAN-Connect Grant Agreement 824989, p. 40). Thus challenges and opportunities need to consider a diverse array of elements of the community to ensure that the project is well-rooted within.

4.2.1. Challenges and opportunities

In terms of community sustainability, the main issue has been the financial structure that is built on the ‘next successful project’ that sustains the continuation of the research, tools and the network from one project life span to the next. In this regard, there is a large amount of invested working hours that is going towards ensuring the future of the collaborative environment as well as providing contributions that are not accounted for in terms of monetary compensation. One consequence of the lack of funding would be the impediment of the new development that could quickly result in the software becoming outdated (e.g., due to no bug fixes or security enhancements). While physical infrastructure, data, services and software are seen as fundamental components that bring the community together, lack of funding is the biggest threat for both the development and maintenance of these, as elements that bring the community together. However, a further challenge is that technical and non-technical infrastructures that are required when implementing applied science projects are not accurately assessed and often are missed in estimating the costs for funding proposals, also not allowing for roles that are involved to be integrated into ‘the community’ beyond the short timeframes of projects or for even shorter periods.

Acknowledging the challenges allows us to identify the opportunities that lie ahead. On the one hand, there is agreement that creation and maintenance of good resources would attract new funding. Here, at least the EU Child Cohort Network has been given as a successful example, as the continuation of the LifeCycle project, sustaining and expanding the existing communities bringing a more diverse geographic representativity.⁵ Another opportunity is seen in cases where the products of the project can be adopted by other consortia, broadening the community. While this is also part of the challenge that there is

⁵ See (17.10.2022): <https://lifecycle-project.eu/for-scientists/the-eu-child-cohort-network/>

much unaccounted work that the community is doing, this means that there are ‘people who care’ who are on the one hand capable of helping other researchers as ‘experienced users’ and that the previous experiences and networking already have allowed the community to be identified that would still stay alive and connected with minimal funding for shorter periods. While a challenge by itself, institutes that are resourceful in their finances may contribute to the catalogues, DataSHIELD, as well as performing federated meta-analyses.

4.2.2. Collected recommendations

Based on the above-listed challenges and opportunities some of the recommendations that are collected are as follows:

- Improving the external communication and network links so that other relevant consortia become aware and can join the effort;
- Making sure that expertise and individuals holding advisory capacity remain in the long term, allowing continuation of building up the community-level expertise as well keeping the existing links;
- Enhancing the dissemination of publications to a broader community as well as ensuring that good publications are produced;
- Establishing links with other or new EU-funded consortia;
- Ensuring that the catalogue and the infrastructure are continuously used and updated, observing that the widespread use and motivation to use within the community is also a prerequisite for financial sustainability and maintenance;
- Demonstrating the societal need and relevance for health beyond disseminating successful publications, for instance, through making visible some examples of collaborations that could be advertised by the entire network, such as cohorts, researchers, institutions as well as directly engaging with key stakeholders;
- Incorporating core infrastructures and data services into the work programs and co-ordinating funding proposals where such prioritisation can be realised;
- Creating and acquiring funds for new consortia in order to adopt and expand the assets of this consortium, above all the existing community.

4.3. Financial sustainability

Financial sustainability necessitates a long-term overview of continuation of the function of the infrastructure in terms of monetary needs. The current financial model in this project, as the qualitative research data shows, relies mainly on follow-up international research projects so that the work that needs to be done can be re-financed based on the acquired previous funding, success and expertise as well as infrastructure and networks already built with an updated vision and workplan for the future through grant proposals. This means for financial sustainability, the major risks to mitigate are both to ensure that such consortia can

be formed and future projects planned will receive funding, but at the same time to broaden the financial repertoire through alternative models of business/financing.

A recent report by the Dutch National Node of BBMRI (van der Stijl & Eijdem, 2019) suggests that there are at least 12 business models for biobanks: project-based, donations-based, contract research, strategic partnership, cost recovery, core facility, service-based, collection on demand, membership, two-sided business, direct-to-consumer business, freemium models. While the case of biobanking cannot be translated one-to-one for EUCAN-Connect, some of the models or combinations of them may be used as reference points for financial sustainability of the project in the longer term. This necessitates, however, that such models are discussed, selected in line with the long-term vision and tested.

4.3.1. Challenges and opportunities

The main challenge for financial stability in this project lies at the heart of the projectification-focused way of knowledge production (Felt, 2022). While there is a continuous reliance on research funding, 'maintaining' an existing infrastructure is often not within the scope of major funding agencies' programs. This on the one hand means that the resources that are produced are put at risk, in terms of further development and maintenance, if the funding for the next projects are not received and on the other hand the situation does not provide any incentives for the local institutions to provide continuous and foreseeable financial support, resulting in further drawbacks in terms of recruiting and sustaining the workforce, especially those staff who are in precarious positions or technical/support teams. Financial challenges are not merely related to the risk of not being able to get renewed funding for future projects, but they also relate to the existing funding where the resources allocated for ('base' funding) is relatively small to continue the 'catalogue' and 'central analysis service' optimally. Similarly, the cohorts/local institutions often have limited to no funding for recruiting personnel for many tasks, such as maintaining the local services. Furthermore, the community that is reached and comprises the project consortium is not as comprehensive, e.g. in terms of the European landscape more countries could be involved, more researchers from around the globe could be trained to expand the network.

While the challenges and risks relate to the 'projectified' way of sustaining the work other than research, opportunities exist in terms of developing and testing models for non-research focused funds, for instance cost-recovery or potential models from the biobanking field as listed above. It has been noted in discussions that there is a growing need for involving the industry partners in grant proposal schemes of some national funding agencies and this may be turned into an opportunity by establishing long term partnerships. Often unseen or invisible aspects of the expertise gained in previous projects is the ability to successfully manage large projects, which can be used as leverage to spearhead multiple

efforts, specifically noting that the funding agencies and the EC would opt for continued support of functional infrastructures, rather than building from scratch.

4.3.2. Collected recommendations

Based on the above-listed challenges and opportunities some of the recommendations that are collected are as follows:

- Making use of the expertise gained in previous funding calls by thoroughly exploring the entire repertoire of potential funding resources holistically;
- Coordinating the planned funding applications not to duplicate, but complement towards the goal of 'efficient input - large output';
- Increasing the usability of different and seemingly disparate tools, products and projects further, and not duplicating a similar effort, but rather maintaining the 'togetherness' and 'compatibility' as well as 'visibility' of the infrastructure and highlighting this in new funding proposals;
- Stressing the amount of work and funding that the effort has received and the capacity and capability achieved to justify the immense need for maintaining funds as well as research and development;
- Considering possibilities of adoptions at different levels by larger/smaller initiatives, e.g. efforts for getting the catalogue into EOSC, as well prioritising efforts to make visible the 'ready-to-go' services that other projects can absorb;
- Discussing, testing and implementing alternative models of business (see: van der Stijl & Eijdem, 2019);
- Approaching hosting institutes for receiving some 'base level' funding or working together at the local/national/international level to create mechanisms for such funding.

4.4. Organisational sustainability

Organisational sustainability is not easily separable from financial and community sustainability. Here, the focus is often on the elements that need to be kept in the long term and include at least the following in line with the previous discussions: IT infrastructure, knowledge at the local IT departments (e.g. regarding DataSHIELD, Armadillo, etc.), central server service and basic IT help (e.g. local servers etc.), DPO, advisors (e.g., on running meta-analysis: logistic procedures, help with the scripts etc.) and cohorts. In this regard, we have identified challenges and opportunities to come up with specific recommendations in terms of organisational sustainability.

4.4.1. Challenges and opportunities

While setting up the DataSHIELD community is an important step towards organisational sustainability, this does not resolve the issues that surround how the organisational needs at the bare minimum are going to be met; even if, across the community, multiple different groups/projects may have funding at any one time, it is unclear how this will be managed at the organisational level. While currently a DataSHIELD Community Constitution⁶ has been proposed, comments collected and approved at the DataSHIELD Conference, shifting from unwritten practices to constitutional organisational structure will take time and will need to adapt to ongoing situations or broader transformative occurrences, e.g. the implementation of the GDPR or the exit of the UK from the European Union in the past. Similarly, developments such as the EU Child Cohort Network (deployment of the LifeCycle, Athlete and LongITools) need to be taken into account. Finally, a major challenge may be the difficulty to decline offers for collaboration or requests that may not be to the advantage of the organisation, especially in terms of allocation of time, human and technical resources including aspects of sustainability. Similarly, there is a tendency at local/national levels to 'keep the resources' especially data, which may cause both difficulties in collaboration, but also in building/expanding organisational structures.

Despite the challenges, the existing developments may open up new opportunities. Above all, the current organisational capacity can be leveraged to better position the effort within broader infrastructures (e.g. European Health Cloud). Similarly, new projects that make use of the DataSHIELD may be motivated to join, leading to both community expansion and financial sustainability as experts become partners. In line with the development of the structure of the DataSHIELD with a constitution⁷, MOLGENIS catalogue might also benefit from a formal governance board which is currently in development in lieu of the informal one that is composed of PIs of partnering projects.

4.4.2. Collected recommendations

Based on the above-listed challenges and opportunities some of the recommendations that are collected are as follows:

- Organising further exchange, collaboration and training possibilities, especially for staff that are in their early career and opening up to beyond the project consortia (e.g. COST-Action, Innovative Training Networks (ITNs), etc.) and supporting project experts;
- Producing and collecting best practices in data collection and management;

⁶ See (17.10.2022):

<https://datashield.discourse.group/t/constitution-and-proposals-to-be-voted-on-at-conference-2022/629>

⁷ See (18.10.2022): <https://datashield.discourse.group/t/datashield-community-constitution-meeting-updates/> (see here especially the sections The [Community Project] Social Contract; The [Community Project] Diversity, Equality and Inclusion statement; and The [Community Project] Code of Conduct that set up a solid governance structure.)

- Having a representative/expert within each cohort (e.g. for harmonisation, answering specific questions);
- Thinking about and discussing the legacy of the project (see for instance: LifeCycle);
- Planning networking activities at the national/local levels as well as at the level of researchers, IT teams, DPOs etc. (e.g. DPOs observing similar issues may come up with common solutions, so rather than duplicating the effort, it can be coordinated but requires adequate resources for networking and CEO/rectorate support as the role of DPO is not project specific but organisational);
- Integrating key individuals into institutional communities as well as not immediately related consortia/projects;
- Obtaining a comprehensive outlook into how work is achieved in other relevant institutions/infrastructures/projects (being connected with key players);
- Continuously updating the organisational needs in line with changes in the vision (e.g. by asking: What items do we want to sustain? What items do we have to sustain? Possibilities of co-branding, e.g. as expert centres or promoted by another organisation etc., and partnership, e.g. research infrastructures like BBMRI etc.).

● 5. Conclusion and Future Actions

Sustainability is not a one time achievable goal but a moving target. In this report, based on the qualitative research conducted and engagement exercises with various stakeholders of this project, we have assessed from the current perspective the situation and produced a set of recommendations for long term sustainability.

While we have proposed concrete recommendations such as creating and maintaining new roles (i.e. ethics and data governance manager, see Annex 1 and 2 respectively), ensuring training for users on the tools provided and experiences shared, we also included tentative recommendations which should be further discussed within the consortium to update the sustainability aspects in line with ongoing developments within and beyond the project's lifespan and the scientific vision of the community.

In a next immediate step within EUCAN-Connect, the work presented here will be complemented with an upcoming paper that discusses sustainability and value making. In addition, this deliverable will inform other deliverables and actions such as most notably MS22 'Evaluation of the implementation of the ELSI governance model complete'. In the remaining year of the project, the EUCAN-Connect partners will strive to ensure adoption of the catalogues and infrastructure components into the core facilities of the partner institutes. Ultimately, more concrete actions (which will build on the recommendations of this report D7.3) will be elaborated in D6.9 "Report on Strategy for Sustainable Network", which will prepare the concrete plan to maintain and expand the update of EUCAN-Connect beyond the scope of the project's lifespan.

In a more strategic outlook and long-term effort, we see the need to urge national funding agencies as well as European funding programmes to incorporate the maintenance and

further development of infrastructure products and services as a key requirement. This may mean that funding agencies accept (part of) maintenance and operational costs or kick-start a development via the project but request maintenance contracts established during the lifetime of the project with the hosting institution but already guaranteed in the proposal phase (e.g. letter of intent by the university).

In conclusion a combination of concrete short-term to mid-term actions but also strategic steps are needed to ensure maintenance beyond a project's lifespan and in line with future proposals and infrastructure initiatives such as EOSC and EHDS.

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7. Annex

○ **Annex 1: Data Governance Manager**

Role: Data Governance Manager

Purpose: governing data including access pipelines and management of data

Location: Task/role within Access Work Package

Duration: half-time to full time position

Key Responsibilities and Accountabilities of the Role

The Data Governance Manager will be responsible for overseeing the processes, roles, policies, standards, and metrics that ensure the effective and efficient use of data, its curation and managing its availability, usability, integrity, and security. The Data Governance Manager will be responsible for ensuring a smooth operation of access and usage of data, especially the access pipeline, the access management system, and access requests. This includes the set up, operation, and maintenance of a data access committee, data management plan, access policy etc. The Data Governance Manager's activities are guided by the principles of due process, fairness, transparency and accountability. The Data Governance Manager will ensure the involvement of relevant internal and external experts to meet the relevant project objectives.

Requirements of the Role

The Data Governance Manager is expected to have a good understanding of data management in a scientific and research context and must have a strong sense for compliance and procedure. A solid understanding of data management, data protection and data security is key. Excellent interpersonal skills, the ability to effectively liaise with colleagues and project partners on all levels in a distributed, international, interdisciplinary environment and the ability to undertake/deliver the required tasks without losing a sense of humour as well as clarity in oral and written communication are essential requirements.

○

- **Annex 2: Ethics Manager**

Role: Ethics Manager

Purpose: Managing ethical requirements during a project lifespan.

Location: Task/role within Coordination Work Package

Duration: 3PM up to full time position (depending on complexity of project and number of partners)

Key Responsibilities and Accountabilities of the Role

The Ethics Manager will be responsible for managing the ethical requirements in the context of a research project. The ethics requirements can be mandatory by national, regional laws and/or regulations or required by the project funders (eg. European Commission). A key role of the Ethics Manager is to ensure that timelines are met to fulfil not only reporting requirements but also match timelines with scientific tasks. This can mean that the set-up of the Data Management Plan needs to match the conditions under which data can be used according to the IC. The information needs to come from the data provider, but the overview needs to be kept by the Ethics Manager. The Ethics Manager also needs to point out where information, approval or similar is missing and ensure that it becomes available or explain why this is not (yet) possible. Wherever necessary, the Ethics Manager will ensure the involvement of relevant internal and external experts to meet the relevant project objectives. Lastly, the Ethics Manager is expected to contribute, and where necessary drive independently internal communication related to the realisation of successful ethics management including keeping a good overview of ethical approvals, their scope and validity, highlighting where specific, external expertise might be needed (eg. Legal Opinion) and keeping an overview and ensuring the response to the ethical requirements requested by the funders (eg. IC copies stored locally, but contact list where to find them and who to contact in case needed by the Ethics Manager centrally) on file.

Requirements of the Role

The Ethics Manager is expected to have a good understanding of ethical, legal and societal aspects, but does not need to be an expert in the field. Rather, the Ethics Manager needs to know when to seek ethics committee approval and/or consult (external) experts to ensure compliance with ethics requirements. The Ethics Manager Skills in project management, keeping timelines and experience in collaborating in international environments and communicating with transdisciplinary teams (e.g., clinical staff, IT, developers, lawyers) are desirable. Excellent interpersonal skills, the ability to effectively liaise with colleagues and project partners on all levels in a distributed, international, interdisciplinary environment and the ability to undertake/deliver the required tasks without losing a sense of humour as well as clarity in oral and written communication are essential requirements.

○ **Annex 3: Mural Exercise on Sustainability**

Figure A1. The result of the latest discussion on sustainability, organised on 13.10.2022.